

THE CONTENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS THROUGH SELF-ASSESSMENT

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Annotation: This article provides an idea of the content of the development of independent cognitive activity in primary school students through self-assessment, modern approaches to it, types of self-education, educational and cognitive competence, as well as methods of self-assessment.

Base words and phrases: self-assessment, independent cognition, motivation, purpose, trust, communication, information, psychology, digital assessment, motivation.

Introduction: in pedagogical practice, sympathy is generated by the teacher to the student who has consistently achieved excellent results. This results in the learner learning unilaterally, only adapting to the assessment criteria the teacher is demanding, completing assignments and tasks. Non-standard, critical, surround thinking in the reader does not develop sufficiently. One of the most important functions of assessment is to motivate the reader to be active on a regular basis, to work on himself, to think independently, to achieve high efficiency. Students have a guiding character to acquire competencies, as well as part-competencies, which must be achieved continuously through the evaluation criteria presented in the self-assessment sheets. Part-competencies are the organizers of a certain competence, which, with perfect possession, passes from the formation of a certain competence to the stage of development. Taking communicative competence as an example, as part-competencies, one can cite the likes of being able to listen to one's companion, following the etiquette and norms of speaking, communicating virtual.

In particular, through self-assessment in reading science, it is possible to educate students in an independent Mutola culture, content personality qualities, introduce technologies for the development of global thinking, and through this there will be an opportunity to increase the level of reading students.

Self-assessment in readers:

spiritual and educational research related to increasing motivation for Independent Education, conducting scientific and creative research, discussing what they read among their peers;

- working with information on the creation of a database by searching, sorting the necessary information from various sources and a global network;
- it is based on the fact that the understanding of works of art, influenced by them, serves to improve national and Universal competencies, such as the norms of etiquette in society, value, belief in traditions. On the example of reading science, the self-assessment sheet is presented in appendix 7.

It is not necessary to look at the transition to self-education as a special activity that is distinguished from classes in work, communication, physical education. A person educates

himself by participating in the beneficial work of society. If a student comes to the gym, playground, sports field, performs morning gymnastics, he or she will have started self-education.

As a result of our pedagogical observations, we can cite the following types of self-education:

- students' own achievements and shortcomings, awareness of their own ways of life;
- exactingness to oneself, dissatisfaction with oneself, striving to be the best;
- to be able to set specific goals and objectives and to achieve them;
- striving for the goal, firm confidence, Principality, independence, activism;
- moving forward according to a plan, not deviating from anything, in the path of goals and objectives set before him;
- knowledge of the ways and styles of working on oneself;
- a clear activity aimed at maturing oneself in several directions.

Self-assessment is a psychological mechanism for self-control of one's own activity and movement. It is manifested in the relationship of evaluating its goals, the possibility of their implementation, the results of its independent activities. Being able to correctly assess one's own capabilities, comparing one's actions proportionally with the real state, not exaggerating one's achievements, or not being discouraged mentally in the event of bad luck, that is, controlling oneself in any case – is called self-adequate assessment. In 6-10-year-old students, the level of self-adequate assessment will continue to grow to 7 degrees.

Work on oneself as well as self-development are important in the personal development of students. Self-development is determined by analyzing and evaluating its activities, behavior, feedback. By working on themselves, students' efforts towards spiritual, social development, personal maturation become consistent and systematic.

Literature analysis and methods: currently, the test method is widely used in all educational institutions in the control of students' knowledge, as well as in self-assessment. The Test is useful not only for students, but also for teachers. By drawing up a test and putting it into practice, they will have the opportunity to control themselves, their knowledge, the knowledge of students in the discipline in which they teach. Compactly structured tests should reflect the content of all sections of the studied science [8; 130-133-p].

Olima G.Alimova conducted research on how the assessment process was carried out in students. In his research work, he noted that everyone wants to give themselves a good, objective assessment, but how to recognize their personal qualities is not understood by many. Self-assessment is formed by the imaginative imagination of all the concepts accumulated in a person's living years. In childhood, when a person's assessment settles into the brain, he collects information about himself from those around him. If a child receives love, encouragement from his parents, he will get along well when he grows up. The content of the organization of self-awareness of the individual (spiritual values, direction of control, self-assessment, reasoning, assessment of emotional state, social rule) complement each other, and their qualitative essence ensures the formation of the current functions of self-awareness in the form of determining a radical change in the point of view of human social activity [1; 2-42-p].

Researcher B.Alimov s. [2; 364-372p]. studying the practical orientation of modern education, he concludes that the main result of the activities of the educational institution should be not a system of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but a set of the following basic competencies:

1. Meaningful – meaningful-to be able to see the surrounding world, to find its own direction in it, to realize its place and function, to be able to choose the target and meaningful directions of its behavior, to be willing to make quick decisions.
2. Universal – specific aspects of the national and universal culture of the recipient of education, the spiritual foundations of the life of Man and humanity, separately obtained Nations, the cultural foundations of family, social, phenomena and traditions in society, the place of Science and faith in human life, awareness of the methods of effective organization of free time.
3. Training-cognition-preparation of the learner for independent cognitive activity: identification of the goal, planning, analysis, reflection, self-assessment in educational-cognitive activities, the ability to distinguish evidence from prejudices, the ability to have measurement skills, be able to use statistics and other techniques.
4. Informational-the readiness of the educator to work with various sources of information, search, analyze, select, organize, process, store and transfer necessary information.
5. Communicative-the learner's knowledge of the necessary languages, methods of interaction with familiar and unfamiliar people and phenomena, skills of working in a group, acquiring various special tasks in a team.
6. Socio-Labor-the acquisition of knowledge and experience in civil and public activities (civil, observational, carrying out representative duties), in the field of socio-labor (consumer, buyer, producer, client rights), in relation to family relations and duties, in the economic and legal spheres.
7. Personal is the self-development, mental and mental, emotional control and self-support of the learner.

Let's look at the third competence in detail, which is one of the most important competencies. Educational - cognitive competence is a set of competencies in the field of independent cognitive activity, elements of logical, methodological general educational activity, which is consistent with the real objects under study of the student, which includes knowledge and qualifications for determining the goal, planning, analysis, reflection, assessment of the educational-cognitive process.

By having this competence, the learner will have the following effective functioning qualifications in relation to the object being studied:

- to be able to apply knowledge directly in a life situation;
- master the methods of movement in non-standard situations;
- the problem was solved by the heuristic method by the clock [2; 364-372].

Research methodology: in the educational system, there are usually two groups of quality descriptions: the quality of the process aimed at achieving the planned results and the quality of the educational result. The description of the second group clearly reflects the normative requirements of the results of education, the degree of conformity with respect to the social and personal results of the learners. The purpose of the assessment can be considered as establishing the conformity of the results obtained in a general way with the intended result or initial assumptions. At each stage of training, the goal is determined, the tasks are set, taking into account the content of the preparation. The following tasks of monitoring the formation of competencies can be distinguished:

presupposes the observation of the degree of formation of diagnostic – competencies in the application;

- prognostic – competencies consist in determining the main trends in the degree of formation of the moment and drawing up a plan for predicting the prospect;
- corrective task – the clock presupposes the identification and solution of problems;
- motivational task – focused on encouraging participants in the educational process to develop themselves independently.

The innovational tools of evaluation include: rating score system, Portfolio, keys, situational assignments, projects, teamwork of coursework, departmental, roll, organizational-activity space [5; p.191].

Self-assessment in primary school students is significant for the following educational effects:

1. Acceptance of their own learning outcomes, abilities, learning potential, as well as their own "I" by comparing them with others.
2. Various self-assessment technologies involve the students' acceptance of themselves through the acceptance of others, that is, the use of the information that the surrounding gives in their relationships again. It helps other students learn about their attitudes towards themselves through attitudes, words, feelings, behavioral reactions.
3. Acceptance in students through the result of their educational activity, that is, the assessment of what the student did. This reinforces the idea of the opportunities available to the students themselves.
4. Acceptance of oneself through an assessment given to one's appearance.

The objectives of the training that allows the development of the individual can be as follows:

- a) to increase their social responsibility, to cultivate their ability to engage in an active relationship with others;
- b) the formation of an active social position and the development of the ability to make changes in their lives;
- c) raising the cultural and psychological level. Common goals are carried out in private tasks, namely: the formation of the ability to correctly assess oneself, the diagnosis and correction of personal qualities, the elimination of communicative barriers, the assimilation of individualized methods of interpersonal communication.[6; 42-p].

In order to increase the motivation of students to read and learn, to develop a responsible attitude towards their educational process, constructive feedback, that is, feedback culture, is introduced in the educational classes. This provides opportunities for the formation of learning advice, feedback, suggestions, and assessment of learned knowledge, skills, and competencies among the teacher and students. There are a number of tools for students' self-assessment, the purpose of which is to provide an opportunity for them to evaluate the educational process and their own participation in it by themselves. Such tools can be attributed to self-assessment sheets, self-assessment conversations, self-assessment dialogues in conversations involving parents, teachers and students, presentation of their own educational activities.

It aims to assess students' interest, base competencies and academic performance – questionnaires aimed at students' ability not only to know, but also to implement, fulfill. While self-assessment of students increases their reflective competencies in them, on the other hand, it performs a data base for the teacher to effectively organize the next class of classes. Self-assessment allows you to assess interdisciplinary knowledge, skills and competencies, and not within the framework of one discipline. Also, self-assessment serves as a foundational resource for conversations with parents about the learner's appropriation when comparing to

a teacher's or other specialist's assessment.

As part of the study, attention was paid to assessment sheets that combined feedback culture with self-assessment. During the learning process, the teacher will be able to react to students through a "data-based feedback" such as "your answer is right or wrong", "the answer (solution) is completely done", "attention should be paid to the following aspects". Through self-assessment, this relationship is expressed in assessment sheets. One important aspect of Feedback culture is its clear separation from praise. In self-assessment methods, attention was also paid to these aspects.

Self-assessment methods are improving from year to year. An analysis of the scientific literature confirms the presence of the following methods:

1. The student who does the job will make a self-assessment. Then his work is evaluated by the teacher, both grades are compared, and the degree of objectivity of the first grade is determined.
2. After an oral response, the teacher asks the answering student what grade can be put on himself. Then he turns to the class and asks to evaluate the answer of his comrades by points. However, in order to formulate self-assessment, it is not enough to involve students in the activities of assessment of e.g. [4; 175-p].

Analysis and results: in the process of assessment, it will be necessary to fully familiarize students with the content of the assessment criteria and, through this, the achievable results of the lesson, science will be expressed. So, the self-assessment carried out makes it possible to determine the ratio of the benchmark between existing and necessary results. By comparing their results by étalon, one gets an assessment of their performance and a complete picture of the shortcomings that they are allowing. Self-assessment is of great importance in the fact that the student is an active subject in teaching.

One of the main pedagogical activities of the teacher in teaching is the management of the cognitive activity of students. The effective organization of this activity makes it possible to successfully carry out the planning of educational and cognitive activities of students, increase the motivation of students, clarify educational goals, Control and assessment.

One of the most common types of self-assessment is acquisition diagnosis sheets. These leaflets reflect all aspects of the course process and dictate the attitude of the student. Through this, the student evaluates his participation, while on the other hand, the lesson is assessed by the teacher professionally, organized according to didactic principles, educational goals of the lesson and continuity of expected results, educational methods, tools, content applied to ensure this continuity. Acquisition diagnosis sheets are based on democratic principles, exaggerating the "culture of feedback" in education. These leaflets regularly provide students with information about the purpose of the learning process, the expected results and the base competencies they must achieve through it. This helps to increase student motivation.

Assessment of the results of oneself and others by students is widely recognized as a type of upbringing. Students gain skills such as expressing their independent opinions, expressing different perspectives, imagining themselves in the place of others, and positively accepting the opinion of others. It also educates aspects such as the culture of treatment in students, appreciation and recognition of other people's work, finding and expressing worthy opinions. The classroom environment also becomes transparent, with advantages among students not only through comparison, grouping, but also through the comprehensive development of

students, recognition of the strengths of each student.

Acquisition diagnosis sheets promote learning from errors and errors in the student's learning-learning process, providing comprehensive information for parents on which aspect to support their child. By assessment, however, it is considered impossible to access such information.

Self-assessment serves as a "guide" in determining the direction of students for the process of obtaining independent education in addition to the educational process. In place of the conclusion, it can be said that self-assessment is inextricably and inextricably linked with self-development and is considered educational, educational, spiritual, motivational, individual.

Self-assessment depends on the class, the study environment in the team. Through this, students will be able to realistically assess their academic performance and learning progress. Below is a review of self-assessment technologies for elementary school students. This in turn allows students to effectively organize support for self-assessment.

The fact that self-assessment is carried out in parallel with digital assessment is also seen as an important competence for the personal development of students. Through this, students include monitoring their activities, reacting reflectively, planning self-development, and barricading learning "thinking far" (sustainability). Digital assessment, i.e., is the need for analysis of a traditional assessment process from a socio-psychological point of view. In front of all students in the classroom, the transparent notification of student grades by the teacher, reading by students only for a good grade, in turn does not fully correspond to the concept of competently approached teaching, which is presented in the state educational standards. The weakening of the interest of students receiving unsatisfactory assessments in the sciences, the negative display of the student's psyche is encountered in pedagogical practice. The transformation of assessment into a first-class activity in the educational process prevents the implementation of educational goals. There are a number of negative aspects to this frequent assessment in adolescence. The reader's confidence in himself and his own success is weakened above all. It is from the assessment that problem situations arise between students who are reading for good and excellent grades compared to a student who has received an unsatisfactory grade.

Self-assessment is the skill of being able to analyze oneself realistically. Self-assessment is important for students to evaluate their educational activities, their participation in it, the effectiveness of reading and learning, the development of learning at the required level, the attitude of the "time-learning materials – content" section, the assessment, analysis of their activities, assessment of their strengths and weaknesses, and the selection of an effective strategy in subsequent learning processes. Self-assessment is based on the purpose and criteria of education, although it aims at students' educational outcomes. Due to the fact that self-assessment is carried out in a subjective way, the original result carries a high or low risk of assessment. Self-assessment supports personal development, motivation, and positivity of school outcomes.

Students develop self-esteem and a sense of confidence in their abilities through self-assessment. It is important to realize that it is necessary to adequately fulfill obstacles, certain requirements for achieving positive results in reading and for personal development to be continuous, which is one of the important functions of self-assessment. Realizing the pedagogical importance of self-assessment, the productive and purposeful use of self-assessment technologies in the educational process of primary school teachers is achieved in

the acquisition of competencies related to the subject to be acquired, presented in state educational standards. When determining the competencies ("necessary state") and the "existing state" of students, self-assessment is performed in a functional task, ultimately serving to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Conclusion: in short, self-assessment is widely used not only in pedagogical practice, but also in a number of areas. In particular, it is widely used in the fields of psychology, management, social, and in determining the potential, personal attitude, current state, personal positivity of an individual. Self-assessment is of a personal-motivational nature, developing students' skills such as making personal decisions, choosing a profession, being able to plan their future, assessing their own capabilities.

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